

Simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) and copper(II) in alloys using diacetylmonoxime benzoylhydrazone (DMBH)

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Diacetylmonoxime benzoyl hydrazone (DMBH) reagent has been used for the determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} by spectrophotometric method. The reagent provides intense yellow colour reaction with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in basic medium. The maximum colour intensity is observed in pH range 8.0–10.0. The compositions of nickel and copper complexes of DM BH as determined by Job's and molar ratio methods are 1 : 2 and 1 : 1 (M : L) respectively. Simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} was carried out by measuring the peak-base line technique at 422.5 and 450 nm respectively. Beer's law is obeyed in the range 0.12–2.4 and 0.125–2.5 µg/ml of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively. The method is carried out without the need for employing simultaneous equation in the determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in synthetic mixtures and alloys.

In continuation of our ongoing work on the analytical applications of two-in-one ligands^{1–4}, we report herein the simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of nickel(II) and copper(II) using diacetylmonoxime benzoyl hydrazone (DMBH). Derivative spectrophotometry⁵ is a very useful technique since it decreases the interferences of foreign ions, and may be advantageously used for the simultaneous determination of metal ions having overlapping spectra.

Results and discussion

The reagent diacetyl monoxime benzoyl hydrazone (DMBH) (I) was prepared by simple condensation of 1 mol of diacetylmonoxime with benzhydrazide as described earlier³. This class of oxime hydrazones are not much studied for the derivative spectrophotometric determination of metal ions. Job's continuous variation method and molar ratio

methods gave the composition of Ni^{II} complex as 1 : 2 and Cu^{II} complex as 1 : 1 (M : L). In basic medium, the ligand presumably exists in enolic form and coordinates to metal ion to give soluble complex.

The colour reactions between Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with DM BH is instantaneous in basic buffer medium at RT. The absorbance of the yellow coloured complexes remains stable for 2 h. Maximum colour intensity is observed in the pH range 8.0–10.00 and 8.0–11.0 for Ni-DMBH and Cu-DMBH complexes, respectively.

Derivative spectra of Ni^{II}-DMBH and Cu^{II}-DMBH complexes: The zero order spectra of solutions of nickel-DMBH (curve a) and copper-DMBH (curve b) complexes in an aqueous basic buffer medium (pH 9) are shown in Fig. 1. The absorption spectra overlap considerably and, therefore, direct spectrophotometric determination of one metal in the presence of another is not possible.

The second derivative spectra of the complexes are also shown in Fig. 1 (curve a' and b'). It can be seen that the peaks of the derivative spectra at higher wavelength are more significant. Derivation leads to generation of sharper bands and gives signals with higher amplitude in the resultant spectra.

The absorption spectra indicate that Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes show minimum amplitude in second derivative spectrophotometric technique at 416 nm (peak) and 372 (peak), 466 (valley), 442 (peak) nm respectively. At 422.5 nm Cu^{II}

I

Fig. 1. Zero order and second order derivative spectrum of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} at pH 9 (a) zero order spectrum of Ni^{II} DMBH system [Ni^{II} 2 × 10⁻⁵ M and DMBH 4 × 10⁻⁴ M] (a') second order derivative spectrum of Ni^{II} DMBH system [Ni^{II} 2 × 10⁻⁵ M and DMBH 4 × 10⁻⁴ M] (b) zero order spectrum of Cu^{II} DMBH system [Cu^{II} 2 × 10⁻⁵ M and DMBH 4 × 10⁻⁴ M], (b') second order derivative spectrum of Cu^{II} DMBH system [Cu^{II} 2 × 10⁻⁵ M and DMBH 4 × 10⁻⁴ M]

complex has zero crossing which is independent of the metal ion concentration and at this wavelength Ni^{II} has an appreciable amplitude. On comparing Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} second derivative spectra, it can be observed that Ni^{II} has zero or very negligible amplitude at 450 nm while at 450 nm, the amplitude of Cu^{II} is appreciable and proportional to the concentration of the metal ion. Hence simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} has been carried out by measuring the peak-base line technique at 422.5 and 450 nm respectively without employing the simultaneous equations.

Calibration plots have been constructed at 422.5 nm and 450 nm by plotting the derivative amplitude against the concentration of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively. The plots thus obtained are linear for obeying the relationships

$$Ni^{II} A_{422.5} = 0.0904C + 0.0008$$

$$Cu^{II} A_{450} = 0.0505C + 0.0009$$

The simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in synthetic mixture was car-

ried out by employing the recommended procedure and the results are presented in Table 1

Table 1. Second derivative simultaneous determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in synthetic mixtures

Amount (ppm)		Error %			
Taken	Found*	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}		
Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}
0.705	1.018	0.699	1.015	+0.85	-0.30
0.705	1.273	0.710	1.252	+0.70	-1.60
0.705	1.527	0.699	1.478	-0.85	-3.20
0.705	1.782	0.688	1.765	-2.20	-0.95
0.705	2.066	0.710	2.018	-0.70	-0.90
0.705	0.762	0.705	0.760	0.00	-1.40
0.939	0.762	0.957	0.780	+1.90	+2.03
1.174	0.762	1.162	0.762	-1.00	0.00
1.409	0.762	1.420	0.759	+0.80	-0.40
1.643	0.762	1.635	0.759	-0.50	-0.40

*Average of three determinations

Interference : The effect of some of the ions which often accompany nickel and copper has been studied in the determination of 1.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ni^{II} and 1.3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Cu^{II} . The tolerance limit of a foreign ion was taken as the amount of foreign ion required to cause an error of $\pm 2\%$ in the amplitude. The tolerance limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) values of diverse ions in the second derivative mode in the determination of 1.2 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ni^{II} and 1.3 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Cu^{II} respectively are : triethanolamine (7183, 2065), thioglycolic acid (530, 425), citrate (1057, 843), tartrate (819, 670), iodide (725, 540), thiosulphate (575, 520), oxalate (470, 495), bromide (420, 410), thiourea (375, 345), nitrate (315, 300), urea (295, 305), acetate (315, -), thiocyanate (9290, 270), chloride (185, 160), phosphate (500, 195), fluoride (98, 100), sulphate (-, 405), W^{VI} (9150, 170), Mo^{VI} (105, 83), Sn^{II} (30, 53), Cr^{VI} (10, 12), Pd^{II} (16, -), Fe^{III} (-, 10), Mn^{II} (12, 8), Al^{III} (25, 60), Zn^{II} (15, 0.5), V^{V} (43, 33). The tolerance limit values of Cu is more in the presence of thiourea (263 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). Al^{III} was masked with triethanolamine (1500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) hence tolerance limit values of Al^{III} is increased.

Applications : The method developed has been applied for the simultaneous determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in aluminium alloy, BAS 106 and NTPC ball bearing materials.

Alloy materials (0.25 g) dissolved in aqua-regia according to procedure described earlier³. Suitable aliquots of sample containing Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were analysed according to the second derivative procedure for the simultaneous determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} . The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Simultaneous determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in alloy samples

Sample	Certified value (%)		Amount found (%) [*]		Standard deviation	
	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}	Ni^{II}	Cu^{II}
Al alloy ^a	1.02	1.17	1.02	1.18	-0.05	-0.25
BAS 106 ^b	1.93	4.10	1.89	4.26	-2.00	-3.90
NTPC ball bearing material ^c	10.00	4.50	10.05	4.55	0.50	-1.10

^{*}Average of five determinations.

^aAl alloy : Fe, 0.3%; Mn, 1.2%; Si, 18.5%; Al, 77%; ^bBAS 106 : Fe, 0.43%; Mn, 0.19%; Si, 0.29%; Mg, 1.61%; rest Al; ^cNTPC ball bearing material Cr, 6.5%; Mn, 2%.

Aluminum is masked with triethanolamine.

Experimental

The reagent was prepared by refluxing diacetylmonoxime (1 mmol) and benzhydrazide (1 mmol) as de-

scribed earlier³. A 0.01 M reagent solution was prepared in DMF, stable for 24 h. 1M HCl-1M sodium acetate (pH 0.5-3.5); 0.2M NaOAc-0.2M AcOH (pH 4-6) and 2M NH_3Cl -2M NH_4OH (pH 8-11) solutions were used. The standard stock solutions containing 590 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Ni^{II} and 635 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Cu^{II} were prepared in water from $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (both Qualigens) and standardized gravimetrically and iodometrically⁶. The solutions were suitably diluted to obtain standard working ($10^{-3}/10^{-4}$) solution of metal ions. Solutions of diverse ions of suitable concentration were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals.

Recommended procedure :

(a) **Determination of nickel^{II} and copper^{II} (second-order)** :

An aliquot of the solution containing 0.25 to 2.50 μg of Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} . 10 ml of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl-NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer solution (pH 9.0) and 1 ml of 0.01 M DMBH were mixed in a 25-ml volumetric flask and the reaction mixture diluted up to the mark with distilled water. The second derivative spectra of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with DMBH complexes were recorded. The peak height method (h) was followed for the determination of metal ions. The peak height at 416 nm and 372 (p), 406 (v), 442 (p) nm is proportional to the concentration of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} respectively. Therefore, peak-height method (416 nm) for Ni^{II} and peak-valley method (406 and 442 nm) for Cu^{II} were employed for the construction of calibration plots.

(b) **Simultaneous second derivative spectrophotometric determination of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}** :

An aliquot of the solution containing Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} in the optimum concentration range, 10 ml of $\text{NH}_4\text{Cl-NH}_4\text{OH}$ buffer solution (pH 9.0) and 1 ml of 0.01 M DMBH solution were mixed in a 25-ml standard flask and the reaction mixture was made up to the mark with distilled water. The second derivative amplitude was measured at 422.5 and 450 nm and the amounts of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were computed from calibration graphs.

A Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer equipped with 1.0 cm quartz cells and an Elico LI-120 pH meter were used.

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